

Point cloud filtering based on multi-scale coefficients of elevation variation for UAV-based terrain modelling

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Abstract—Surface vegetation will have a significant impact on the accuracy of terrain modeling based on Unoccupied Aerial Vehicles (UAV). Therefore, vegetation removal is an important step in terrain modeling. Removing vegetation accurately is the key to ensuring the accuracy of the terrain model and it is also the foundation for constructing high-precision DEMs. For different terrain features and regions, different methodologies have their advantages and disadvantages. However, these methods have certain commonalities and are mainly based on the filtering of point cloud morphological features at a unique scale. Over-segmentation, under-segmentation, and low precision have been problems in densely or lowly vegetated areas. In this study, we proposed a filtering method based on the multi-scale elevation variation coefficient. Firstly, different-scale virtual grids (VGs) are constructed from point clouds. Secondly, any two VGs are subtracted from each other to obtain the difference of the VG's surface (elevation difference) (DVG). Thirdly, the elevation variation coefficient of DVG is calculated. The point cloud is scale integrated through the virtual grid (VG) and its elevation values produce a range of variances. This degree of variation reflects the surface characteristics that are reflected in the point cloud at different scales. A variation coefficient threshold is then used to filter vegetation points from terrain points because the variation is generally higher in DVG in vegetation areas. Finally, the optimal variation coefficient threshold is analyzed. To evaluate the accuracy of terrain modelling more precisely, we used the method recommended by the International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (ISPRS) for quantitative analysis. The experimental results show that the proposed method can accurately remove vegetation points and reserve ground points in areas with low vegetation coverage with Type I error, Type II error, and Total error of 9.20%, 5.83%, and 7.68%, respectively. Meanwhile, it lays the foundation for the rapid establishment of high-precision DEMs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unoccupied Aerial Vehicles (UAV) play an important role in the development of digital terrain modelling [1]. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) constructed with terrain modelling requires the removal of surface information, such as vegetation. The quality and accuracy of DEMs are determined by the accuracy of surface feature removal or by the precision of ground point selection. Fast and accurate vegetation removal is key to DEMs construction [2].

The separation of ground and non-ground measurements from the point cloud as a filtering process is a prerequisite for vegetation removal. Many point cloud filtering algorithms have been proposed in recent years, and these algorithms can be mainly classified as slope-based algorithms [3], triangulated irregular network-based (TIN-based) algorithms [4], machine learning-based algorithms, surface-based algorithms [5], and mathematical morphology-based algorithms [6]. The slope-based filtering is performed by selecting a suitable threshold. These methods are simple and efficient but do not perform well in areas with complex terrain, especially in areas with rugged terrain and low vegetation cover [7]. The TIN-based method has a better filtering effect in urban areas and can adapt to areas with discontinuous topography, but the method is ineffective in mountainous areas with more vegetation cover [8]. The machine learning based approach simplifies the filtering process to a point cloud binary classification problem.. Although these methods can achieve good accuracy, the pretraining samples are labor-intensive to label and train [9]. Surface-based methods are not satisfactory in areas containing complex terrain, such as both flat and steep slopes [5]. Mathematical morphology-based algorithms' most important aspect is the choice of the filtering window scale. Large objects cannot be effectively removed when the window scale is small, and terrain detail is easily missed when it is large.

For different terrain features and regions, different methodologies have their advantages and disadvantages. However, these methods have certain commonalities and are mainly based on the filtering of point cloud morphological features at a unique scale [10]. The characteristics of ground and non-ground points at different spatial scales are distinctly different. It is difficult to achieve high accuracy by relying on a unique scale for filtering. In recent years, researchers have proposed various improved filtering methods to address the inadequacies of a single scale [4, 11, 12]. However, these improved multiscale filtering methods perform their respective single information extraction from the perspective of scale progression. The different amounts of surface information contained in topographic data at different scales are not considered.

The virtual grids (VGs) were composed of multiple cubes of equal length and width. If point cloud data are integrated at different scales through the VGs, the elevation values produced will be associated with a range of variations. This degree of variation reflects the surface characteristics (e.g., vegetation and topography) that are reflected in the point cloud at different scales. If the degree of an elevation variation in point cloud data at different scales can be quantified, it will provide a new approach to terrain modelling. The elevation variation coefficient (EVC) is an important topographic factor in digital terrain analysis [13]. It can be used to quantify the degree of elevation variation. EVC has been applied to geomorphology [14]. Therefore, this paper proposes a novel digital terrain modeling algorithm that is capable of extracting and quantifying differences in surface features at different scales.

II. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

A. Area and Data

The test area is located in Xining City, Qinghai Province, China. The Da Jiang Inspire1 UAV, equipped with the SONYEXOR sensor and 20mm fixed focus lens, and Pix4Dmapper software was used to complete image matching, aerial triangulation, and dense matching point cloud production. The study area covered an area of 23439.46 square meters, including 4453114 discrete point clouds. In addition to ground points, it also contained a large number of vegetation and a small number of man-made ground objects. The vegetation mainly included two types of dense low vegetation, which were connected in strips in some areas and isolated in others. The orthophoto image and original point cloud data in the test area are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure. 1 Image and original point cloud of the test area. (a) Image of Xining from the UAVs, (b) Original point clouds of Xining from the UAVs.

B. Method

In this study, the point clouds are segmented with the VGs, and each grid contains several elevation points. The different scales of the VGs are represented by different colors. The elevation of each VG is determined according to specific criteria. Fig. 2 is a schematic diagram of the VGs.

Figure. 2 Schematic diagram of the VGs. (a) 3-D representation of the VGs, (b) 2-D representation of the VGs.

The spatial scale of VG directly impacts its data volume, representation accuracy, and the calculation of topographic factors such as EVC, slope, and slope direction. Different spatial scales of VGs contain different topographic and geomorphological information. As the spatial scale of the VG increases, the accuracy of the description of surface details is gradually smoothed, and the information is gradually integrated. On the contrary, as the spatial scale of the VG becomes finer, the description of the details of the surface gradually increases, and the smaller its spatial scale, the more accurately and realistically the detailed features of the surface within the region are reflected. Therefore, calculating the elevation differences of VGs at different spatial scales can reflect discrepancy of surface information contained in VGs at different scales (e.g., vegetation). As shown in Fig. 3, the white points represent the ground points and the black points represent the vegetation points. The high-precision topographic model section generated under the small-scale VG has a high precision in describing the surface details. The low-precision topographic model section generated under the large-scale virtual grid has a rough representation of the surface details, in which surface features tend to be flat. The elevation difference of VGs at different

spatial scales was calculated, and significant fluctuations appear at the edges of the vegetation points.

Figure. 3 Schematic diagram of topographic model section.

Elevation variation coefficient (EVC) is an important terrain factor in digital terrain analysis. As a variable that can reflect the dispersion degree of data elevation average, it is the ratio of standard deviation and average value of data elevation points, which can reflect the difference of terrain characteristics. The calculation method is shown in Formula (1). The use of EVC can directly represent the variation of elevation in different-scale VGs and minimize the effect of noises.

$$EVC = H_{std}/H_{mean} \quad (1)$$

where, EVC is the elevation variation coefficient of the cell VG in the analysis area, which objectively reflects the difference in the elevation change of the terrain in the analysis area. H_{std} is the elevation standard deviation in VG statistical window. H_{mean} is the elevation mean value in VG statistical window.

III. RESULTS

A. Accuracy Analysis

The terrain modelling method based on elevation variation coefficient is applied to test areas to evaluate the accuracy of this method. The specific parameter selection is analyzed in the test area as an example. Table I shows the parameters used in the test area for this experiment.

TABLE I. THRESHOLD OF OUR FILTERING METHOD

Parameters	Threshold
large-scale VG	3.2m
small-scale VG	0.2m
pixel neighborhood	3×3pixel
variation coefficient threshold	1.5

We manually classified the ground and vegetation points as the reference data. The results of the proposed method were then compared with the reference data. To evaluate the accuracy of terrain modelling more precisely, we used the method recommended by the International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (ISPRS) for quantitative analysis [15].

Error results in the test area are shown in Table II. The Type I error, Type II error, and Total error in the test area are 9.20%, 5.83%, and 7.68%, respectively. The Type I error is larger than the Type II error, which is due to the high amount of vegetation-covered areas in the study area, resulting in the high Type I error. The purpose of point cloud filtering is to accurately extract ground points and ensure terrain accuracy. Therefore, Type II errors should be controlled first. It is also possible to sacrifice Type I errors to ensure that the filtered data does not contain vegetation areas.

TABLE II. RESULT OF THE TEST DATA

Reference	Result			Error (%)	
	Ground Points	Vegetation Points	Sum		
Test Area	Ground Points	2215181	224442	2439623	TypeI: 9.20
	Vegetation Points	117420	1896071	2013491	TypeII: 5.83
	Sum	2332601	2120513	4453114	Total: 7.68

B. Accuracy Comparison

In order to measure the final terrain modelling accuracy of this method, Cloth Simulation Filtering (CSF), Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN), and Progressive Morphological Filtering (MPRP) are used to model the terrain in the test areas. The filtering result and error comparison of methods are shown in Figure 4 and Table III.

Figure. 4 Filtering result comparison. (a) filtering result of our method. (b) filtering result of CSF. (c) filtering result of TIN. (d) filtering result of MPRP. (e) DSM of the test area. (f) DEM by filtering result of our method.

It can be seen from Figure 4 (a) that the filtering algorithm can better filter the ground point and effectively remove a large amount of vegetation cover. It can better deal with areas with low vegetation coverage and preserve the details of terrain. It can be seen from the comparison of Figure 4 (f) with Figure 4 (e) that compared with the Digital Surface Model (DSM), the DEM retains the topographic features of the region and eliminates vegetation points effectively. Compared with Figure 4 (a), Figure 4 (b), Figure 4 (c), Figure 4 (d), it can be seen from Figure 4 (b) that the CSF can remove most of the vegetation, but the effect is poor on the low vegetation distributed in patches, and the terrain boundary is eliminated where the slope changes greatly. It can be seen from Figure 4 (c) that the TIN preserves the boundary of terrain, but the effect of vegetation removal is poor in areas with large terrain gradient. It can be seen from Figure 4 (d) that the MPRP works well in flat terrain areas, but it does not work well in some areas with large topographic relief, and the algorithm has many parameters that are difficult to coordinate with each other.

TABLE III. FILTERING ERROR COMPARISON OF THREE METHODS

Sample	Error	Our method	CSF	TIN	MPRP
Test Area	Type I (%)	9.20	22.56	2.26	13.27
	Type II (%)	5.83	14.09	43.51	11.56
	Total (%)	7.68	18.73	20.91	12.50

The results in Table III show that the method based on multi-scale EVC is superior to the methods of CSF, TIN, and progressive morphology in terms of type I error, type II error, and total error in the terrain modelling results of the test area. In general, the filtering algorithm proposed in this study is more suitable for low vegetation dense coverage areas. It can ensure that the low vegetation is filtered and the ground points are kept accurately, which can meet the requirements of generating high-precision DEMs.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we proposed a filtering method that based on the multi-scale elevation variation coefficient. Firstly, different scale virtual grids (VG) are constructed from point clouds. Secondly, any two virtual grids subtracted from each other to obtain the difference of the VG surface (elevation difference) (DVG). Thirdly, the elevation variation coefficient of DVG is calculated. A variation coefficient threshold is then used to filter vegetation points from terrain points because the variation is generally higher in DVG in vegetation areas. Finally, the optimal variation coefficient threshold is analyzed. The experimental results show that the proposed method can accurately remove vegetation points and reserve ground points in areas with low vegetation coverage with Type I error, Type II error and Total error of 9.20%, 5.83%, and 7.68%, respectively. Meanwhile, it lays the foundation for the rapid establishment of high-precision DEMs.

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